

Comparison of Oral Progesterone with Oral Progesterone plus Inj. HCG for the Management of Threatened Miscarriage

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ABSTRACT

Background & Objectives: To compare the efficacy of progesterone alone versus progesterone plus human chorionic gonadotropin for management of threatened miscarriage.

Study design: Randomized controlled trial

Place & duration of study: The study was carried out in department of Obstetrics & Gynecology, CMH Lahore for six months from 12th July 2018 to 12th Jan 2019.

Methods: One hundred females with threatened miscarriage fulfilling inclusion criteria were divided in two groups. In group A, 50 females were given progesterone in oral tablet form plus human chorionic gonadotropin (hCG) as intra-muscular injection, while in group B, 50 females were given (oral only) progesterone till 14 weeks. Females were followed up in OPD on weekly basis till 14 weeks of gestation and efficacy of treatment was compared. Efficacy was defined as successful treatment leading to continuity of pregnancy to second trimester (14 weeks of pregnancy) with no vaginal bleeding and no abdominal discomfort/pain.

Results: The mean age of females in group A and B was 24.10 ± 3.21 and 26.63 ± 6.05 years, respectively. The mean gestational age, BMI and parity of females in group A and B were 10.01 ± 2.84 vs 10.98 ± 1.52 weeks, 25.10 ± 4.43 Kg/m² vs 27.95 ± 3.61 Kg/m² and 3.01 ± 0.84 vs 1.98 ± 1.24 , respectively. Efficacy was 86% with progesterone plus hCG and 42% with progesterone alone for management of threatened miscarriage and it differs significantly among two groups ($P < 0.05$).

Conclusion: Progesterone plus hCG is more effective than progesterone alone for management of threatened miscarriage.

Keywords: Threatened Miscarriage, Early pregnancy, Progesterone

INTRODUCTION

Vaginal bleeding in early pregnancy is not very uncommon. As many as approximately 25% of pregnant women experience bleeding during their first trimester. Spectrum of differential diagnosis includes threatened miscarriage, spontaneous miscarriage and ectopic pregnancy.¹ The incidence of spontaneous miscarriage varies between 15-20%.^{2,3} The etiology varies and is often multifactorial. Idiopathic etiologies could result in 40-50% of threatened miscarriage. Other common factors include fetal chromosomal abnormalities, environmental and immune factors, and maternal endocrine dysfunction. Maternal endocrine disorders especially luteal insufficiency are fairly common.^{4,5} Progesterone deficiency is recognized to be associated with insufficient endometrial maturation and inadequate regulatory mediators such as interleukins.

Several supportive therapies have been advocated. These include bed rest, avoidance from coitus and a simple wait and watch policy.⁶ However keeping in view the commonest cause being the maternal endocrine problems, we rely mainly on hormonal treatment with progesterone or hCG. Progesterone maintains pregnancy by enhancing uterine quiescence. A number of studies have shown efficacy of

progesterone in threatened miscarriage.⁷⁻¹¹ However, overall data on the use of progesterone for threatened miscarriage remains conflicting. There has also been much interest in the use of hCG to treat threatened miscarriage. It has negligible side effects but it is available only in injection form.^{12,13}

The objective of this study was to compare the efficacy of oral progesterone alone and progesterone plus hCG for management of threatened miscarriage. Theoretically, addition of hCG to progesterone can help in reducing the number of incidents of miscarriage. But not enough data is available in literature to support the use of combination therapy. The study may help to improve our practice and prevent females from adverse pregnancy outcomes associated with threatened miscarriage.

PATIENTS AND METHODS

This randomized controlled trial was conducted in the obstetrics & gynaecology department, Combined Military Hospital (CMH), Lahore from 12th July 2018 to 12th January, 2019. Sample size of 100 cases; 50 cases in each group was calculated with 90% Power of test, 5% level of significance and taking expected percentage of efficacy i.e. 83.3% with oral progesterone (dydrogesterone 10 mg) plus hCG and 56.7% with oral progesterone (dydrogesterone 10 mg) alone for management of threatened miscarriage. Non-probability consecutive sampling technique was used. Females of

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age 18-40 years, parity <5, presenting at gestational age 8-12weeks (on LMP) with threatened miscarriage (which was defined as vaginal bleeding occurring with or without abdominal pain with positive pregnancy test and hCG >12,000mIU/ml between 8-12 weeks of pregnancy) were included in the study. Patients with multiple pregnancy, with non-viable fetus (no fetal heart beat on USG) or with any concurrent medical disorder like febrile illness (malaria, typhoid), hypertension, diabetes mellitus or cardiac problems (on medical record) were excluded from the study.

Approval for the study was taken from the ethical committee. 100 females fulfilling selection criteria were enrolled in the study from OPD of Obs/Gynae department of CMH Lahore. After obtaining informed consent, demographic information (name, age, BMI, gestational age, parity) were recorded. Confounding factors were addressed. Then females were randomly assigned by blind balloting into two equal groups by using lottery method. In Group A, females were given oral Progesterone (Dydrogesterone 10mg twice daily) plus intramuscular inj hCG 5000iu weekly till 14 weeks. In Group B, females were given oral progesterone twice daily till 14 weeks. Patients were followed-up in OPD every week and advised to come early in case of excessive bleeding. Main outcome measures were vaginal bleeding, abdominal discomfort/pain and continuation of pregnancy continued up to second trimester. Efficacy was defined as successful treatment leading to continuity of pregnancy to second trimester (14 weeks of pregnancy) with no vaginal bleeding and no

abdominal discomfort/pain. All this information was recorded on a specially designed proforma. Data was entered and analyzed through SPSS version 21. The quantitative data like age, gestational age and BMI were presented as mean and standard deviation. Qualitative variables like efficacy were presented as frequency and percentage. Chi-square test was applied to compare efficacy in both groups. P-value ≤0.05 was considered as significant. Data was stratified for age, gestational age, parity and BMI. Post-stratification, chi-square test was applied with P-value ≤0.05 considered as significant.

RESULTS

A total of one hundred females were included in this study. In Group A, the mean age of the females with threatened miscarriage was 24.10 ± 3.21 years, while in Group B, the mean age of the females was 26.63 ± 6.05 years. In Group A, the mean gestational age of the females with threatened miscarriage was 10.01±2.84 weeks. In Group B, the mean gestational age of the females with threatened miscarriage was 10.98±1.52 weeks. Majority of patients (50% in group A and 56% in Group B) were in the range of 10-11 weeks. The mean BMI in group A was 25.10 ± 4.43 Kg/m² and in group B was 27.95 ± 3.61 Kg/m². In group A, the mean parity was 3.01±0.84, and in group B it was 1.98±1.24.

In group A, the efficacy was 86% while in group B, the efficacy was 42%. The results were statistically significant (p-value=0.002).

Stratification of data (Efficacy) by effect modifiers including age, gestational age, BMI and parity are given in the Tables 2, 3 and 4.

Table 1: Distribution of patients by age (n=100)

Age in years	Group A (n=50)		Group B (n=50)	
	No. of patients	Percentage (%)	No. of patients	Percentage (%)
18-20	19	38	11	22
21-30	23	46	29	58
31-40	8	16	10	20
Mean ±SD	24.10 ± 3.21 years		26.63 ± 6.05 years	
P-Value*	0.973**			

*Chi-Square test
** Not significant

Table 2: Distribution of patients by Gestational age (n=100)

Gestational age (weeks)	Group A (n=50)		Group B (n=50)	
	No. of patients	Percentage (%)	No. of patients	Percentage (%)
8-9	21	42	17	34
10-11	25	50	28	56
12	4	8	5	10
Mean ±SD	10.01±2.84 weeks		10.98±1.52 weeks	
P-Value*	0.873**			

*Chi-Square test
** Not significant

Table 3: Comparison of patients by Efficacy (n=100)

Group	Efficacy			
	Yes		No	
	n	%	N	%
8-9	43	86	7	14
10-11	21	42	29	58
P-Value*	0.002**			

*Student t test

** Significant

Table 4: Stratification of data (Efficacy) by effect modifier (Gestational age) (n=100)

Gestational Age (Weeks)	Efficacy			
	Group A (n=50)		Group B (n=50)	
	Yes	No	Yes	No
	n(%)	n(%)	n(%)	n(%)
8-9	18 (85.71)	3 (14.28)	7 (41.17)	10 (58.82)
10-11	23 (92)	2 (8)	13 (46.42)	15 (53.57)
12	2 (50)	2 (50)	1 (20)	4 (80)
Total	43 (86)	7 (14)	21 (42)	29 (58)
P value*	**0.590			

*Chi square test

*Not Significant

DISCUSSION

Etiology of threatened miscarriage is multifactorial. Several studies^{4,5,14,15} have pointed out that luteal insufficiency leading to decreased levels of progesterone is a significant issue leading to risk of miscarriage and that forms the basis of our treatment with hormonal therapies. Omar MH¹⁶ et al conducted his study on 154 women with threatened miscarriage with significantly (p=0.037) higher success rate in women treated with dydrogesterone (95.9%) compared with women who received conservative treatment (86.3%).

Similar evidence is obtained from other studies^{17,18}. One study conducted by Peter Toth¹⁷ describes that the combination of progesterone with magnesium or hCG gave promising results in favor of hormonal treatment. Calculating as a percentile, magnesium and progesterone gave 25% reduction in miscarriage (overall miscarriage rate 18.4%) while magnesium and hCG gave 46.8% reduction rate (now over all miscarriage rate of 18.1%). The triple combination of magnesium, progesterone and hCG gave the best outcome reducing miscarriage rate to 16.6%.

A meta analysis conducted by Howard Carp¹⁹ showed substantial reduction in risk of miscarriage with use of dydrogesterone. The 24% miscarriage rate in control women (78/325) was reduced to 13% (44/335) after dydrogesterone administration (11% absolute reduction in the miscarriage rate). He also concluded that therapy

was associated with no significant side effects.

Many other pieces of research work showed significant benefit and risk reduction with use of these hormonal derivatives of progesterone and beta hCG, including the work done by Qureshi⁷, Duan⁸ and Akhtar²⁰. The results of our study are comparable to that conducted by Akhtar et al²⁰ with efficacy of 86% vs 83.33% in group A and efficacy of 42% vs 56.67% in group B respectively. Findings of this study clearly support use of progesterone and inj hCG. Further evidence comes from the study by E Saha et al where continuing pregnancy success rate was higher in women treated with dydrogesterone (79.17%) and highest with Injection hCG (86.36%) compared with women who received no treatment (70%), (p=0.358).⁵ However contradictory results were obtained in some of meta-analysis and studies done by Devaseelan²¹ and Yassae²². Devaseelan²¹ included three studies (312 participants) in his meta-analysis, one of which was of poor methodological quality. The meta-analysis showed that there was no statistically significant difference in the incidence of miscarriage between hCG and 'no hCG' (placebo or no treatment) groups (Risk ratio (RR) 0.66; 95% confidence interval (CI) 0.42 to 1.05). However still there was favorable result when hCG and bed rest were combined, there was a significant reduction in the risk of miscarriage (RR 0.47; 95% CI 0.27 to 0.82). This result however, could be due to poor methodology. He also concluded that hormonal therapy was without any adverse effects on mother or baby. Yassae et al²²

conducted a single blind clinical trial on 60 pregnant females. The study demonstrated that the rate of abortion was reduced (20% versus 33.3%) in women treated with progesterone suppositories. However, the difference was not statistically significant.

We cross tabulated the data with effect modifiers and found that highest efficacy was seen in 21-30 years of age, at 10-11 weeks of gestational age, at the parity range of 1-2 in both groups and statistically, no difference was found between two groups.

This study has certain limitations. This was a single center study with a limited population size. Demography was not uniform as patients were mostly entitled and they belonged to variable strata of population. Cost comparison is a major restraint as hCG injection is very costly and may not be available to all to get beneficial effect for a larger group of population. Blinding (on injection and tablet versus tablet alone) on the part of patient was not included in our study as most of patients as well as the doctor knew what type of treatment they are getting. And so did the doctor know, posing a chance of bias. Nonetheless, overall results proved so promising in favor of combination treatment that we might consider conducting this study on a larger scale in future in double blinding randomized control fashion to gain further evidence.

CONCLUSION

This study concluded that progesterone plus hCG is more effective than progesterone alone for management of threatened miscarriage. More studies on a larger scale may help in establishing that progesterone plus hCG should be given routinely among females with threatened miscarriage.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

This study has no conflict of interest to be declared by any author.

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